

**RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY
APPLIED TO THE RADAR RANGE EQUATION**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to illustrate the technique of response surface methodology to prioritize data collection in a database where confidence factors are assigned to data elements whose accuracy is suspect.

I. INTRODUCTION

If a database contains information in which certain data elements are suspect, confidence factors may be assigned. These confidence factors indicate the degree of confidence in each data element. The database used in this paper had such confidence factors assigned to radar parameters. Using these confidence factors and applying response surface methodology, certain parameters are identified which must be estimated more accurately. In addition to efficiency in data collection, the linear equation produced by the application of response surface methodology, can be used to optimize a radar design. For example, if a desired range is needed and the cost constraints are known, the radar can be designed so as to optimize the range desired at the least cost.

Standards

An R-squared value of 99% will be the minimum standard used for an adequate fit of the model to the data. The R-squared value is the ratio of the sum-of-squares of regression over the sum-of-squares of the total design. This is shown graphically in three-dimensional space below:

FIGURE 1. GEOMETRIC INTERPRETATION OF THE SUM OF SQUARES

The y in the figure above is the equation of the actual data and the \hat{y} is the estimated equation. The squared length of y is the sum-of-squares of the total data and the squared length of \hat{y} is the sum-of-squares of regression. The ratio of these two quantities provides a good estimate if the residual plots reveal no dependent tendency. The R-squared value gives the experimental designer an estimation of how "close" y is to \hat{y} and thus a criteria to determine the adequacy of fit of the linear equation to the data.

Radar Range Equation

The radar range equation used was:

$$R = \left(\frac{P_t G_t G_r \sigma \lambda^2 L}{(4\pi)^3 k T_0 B F_s (S/N)} \right)^{1/4}$$

where,

- R = range
- P_t = peak transmitted power
- G_t = transmitting antenna gain
- G_r = receiving antenna gain
- σ = radar cross section
- λ = wavelength
- L = system losses
- k = Boltzman's constant
- T_0 = standard reference temperature, 290° K
- B = bandwidth
- F_s = standard system noise figure
- S/N = signal-to-noise ratio

II. METHODOLOGY

Application of Response Surface Methodology to Radar Data

For technical or economical reasons, it is frequently not possible to experimentally verify the performance of a radar over its complete range of operation. If measurements can be made at short range, it is desirable to be able to extrapolate these measurements to predict performance at far ranges. It is also desirable to know precisely the effect of the radar's design parameters on its performance so that the design can be optimized. (3:38)

The process of response surface methodology applies linear regression to fit a linear equation to data. It identifies the affect of the radar's design parameters on its performance, this is the reason why this technique was used on the database parameters.

The first step in the process of applying the method of response surface methodology was to extract data from the database. A radar was chosen from the database and was labeled Radar X. The parameters that were extracted from the database were: Power (P), Transmitting Antenna Gain (GT), Receiving Antenna Gain (GR), Frequency (F), Noise Figure (NF), Losses (L), and Bandwidth (B). Since each of these parameters had confidence factors associated

with them (indicating the degree of confidence in that parameter), a range of inaccuracy of this parameter was established based on these confidence factors.

Four different designs were created using different values for the appropriate confidence factors. Design 1 used a 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% range of accuracy for a confidence factor of 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively. For a confidence factor of one, the actual numbers for high and low values were used (0% range of inaccuracy). For a confidence factor of two, a range of plus or minus 5% was created. For a confidence factor of three a range of 10% was created. Finally, for a confidence factor of four, a range of 15% was created. Therefore for a confidence factor of two, the low value was multiplied by 0.95 and the high value was multiplied by a value of 1.05. The low and high values were multiplied by 0.9 and 1.1 respectively for a confidence factor of 3. For a confidence factor of 4 the low and high values were multiplied by 0.85 and 1.15 respectively. The sets of designs with their appropriate ranges of inaccuracy and multipliers are shown below:

Table I. Designs and Associated Confidence Factors

Design	Confidence Factor	Range of Inaccuracy
1	1	0.0%
	2	5.0%
	3	10.0%
	4	15.0%
2	1	0.0%
	2	10.0%
	3	20.0%
	4	30.0%
3	1	10.0%
	2	20.0%
	3	30.0%
	4	40.0%
4	1	20.0%
	2	30.0%
	3	40.0%
	4	50.0%

The extraction of the parameters from the database resulted in seven ranges of inaccuracy for the seven parameters. The next step was to supply a radar cross section and a temperature. The radar cross section was given a range of 5.0 to 30.0 square meters, and the temperature was allowed to range from 273.0 to 300.0 degrees Kelvin.

The final parameter to obtain was the required signal-to-noise ratio. Instead of using a single figure for this number, a range was created using the "extreme" values of the Probability of False Alarm (PFA), Probability of Detection (PD), and Number of pulses incoherently integrated (N). These three were used instead of the single number of signal-to-noise ratio in order to analyze the main effects of each, and their interactions on the radar range. These numbers were extracted from DiFranco and Rubin for a Swerling case I target. (3:380,384) The numbers used for each were:

Table II. High and Low Settings of PFA, PD, and N

	<u>Low</u>	<u>High</u>
PFA	0.693/10 ¹⁰	0.693/10 ¹
PD	15.0%	97.0%
N	1	10

These three ranges varied in all possible ways resulting in eight different required signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios. These were:

Table III. S/N Values and Settings of PFA, PD, and N

<u>PFA</u>	<u>PD</u>	<u>N</u>	<u>S/N (dB)</u>
-1	-1	-1 ^A	10.62 ^B
1	-1	-1	-3.25
-1	1	-1	29.37
1	1	-1	19.37
-1	-1	1	2.8125
1	-1	1	-9.0625
-1	1	1	20.9375
1	1	1	12.81

^A-1 denotes the low setting and 1 denotes the high setting.
^BA three dB correction factor has been subtracted from the chart values of DiFranco and Rubin because the S/N ratios are recorded at the intermediate frequency amplifier not after the detector (3:376)

Once these intervals were derived an applicable design was created. Using the seven factors from the database, the two for radar cross section and temperature, and using the three parameters of probability of false alarm, probability of detection, and number of pulses incoherently integrated, a 12 factor design would be needed. It was important that the two-way interactions and the main effects be confounded with three-way and higher interactions and therefore a design of resolution V was needed. This design confounds the main effects with four-factor interactions, and two-factor interactions are confounded with three-factor interactions. This type of design allows an unbiased estimation of all main effects and two-factor interactions.

A fractional factorial design was desired due to the reduced number of runs required. Box and Draper provides some designs (1:163), but the designs presented were only for factors of 11 or less, and Montgomery offers designs for 10 factors or less. (4:338-339)

A reference in Montgomery's book to an article by Box and Hunter for more Resolution V designs was mentioned. This article was reviewed but did not have a design of resolution V with 12 factors. (2:449-458)

Since a design of 11 factors was presented in Box and Draper's book, a 12 factor design was extrapolated from this design. The extrapolated design is a sixteenth fraction of resolution V and thus would require 256 runs. The method of introducing the remaining 4 factors for the design were generated using the following:

Table IV. Creation of the 12 Factor Design

<u>Column</u>	<u>Confounding Columns</u>
9	1237
(10)	2345
(11)	1346
(12)	2345678

This design was checked to insure its resolution was in fact a resolution V. Confounding the last four columns in all possible ways with themselves resulted in the following:

Table V. Confounding Columns of the 12 Factor Design

<u>Columns</u>	<u>Confounding Columns</u>
9	1237
(10)	2345
(11)	1346
(12)	12345678
9(10)	14579(10)
9(11)	24679(11)
9(12)	45689(12)
(10)(11)	1256(10)(11)
(10)(12)	1678(10)(12)
(11)(12)	2578(11)(12)
9(10)(11)	35679(10)(11)
9(10)(12)	23689(10)(12)
(10)(11)(12)	3478(10)(11)(12)
9(11)(12)	13589(11)(12)
9(10)(11)(12)	12489(10)(11)(12)

As can be seen from the Confounding Columns column, there is no entry with less than four columns, and thus a design of resolution V has been created (I = 12379,2345(10),1346(11), 12345678(12)). Therefore, the design created was a 2_v^{12-4} design and the core design used was a 2^8 design requiring 256 runs.

Programs

Using the radar range equation and the Fortran programming language, a computer program was created that would read in the z matrix (the matrix that sets whether the parameter is high or low) and as its output, would append the range calculated with the parameters at their appropriate settings. For example, the following could be a row of settings from a z matrix that would be read into the program:

Table VI. Settings of Factors in a Z Matrix

-1	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	1	1	-1
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This could produce a range in meters of 8478.84 from a certain radar and the output from the Fortran program would be:

Table VII. Sample of an Output from the Fortran Program

-1	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	1	1	-1	8478.84
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Each column is the setting for a given parameter and is always in the order of: Power (P), Transmitting Antenna Gain (GT), Receiving Antenna Gain (GR), Frequency (F), Noise Figure (NF), Losses (L), Bandwidth (B), Radar cross section (RCS), Temperature (T), Probability of False Alarm (PFA), Probability of Detection (PD), and Number of pulses Incoherently Integrated (N).

Response surface methodology uses an equation to transform the data from values to numbers between 1.0 and -1.0. The high values become 1.0 and the low values become -1.0. This is accomplished by subtracting the average of the high and low values and dividing by half the difference between the high and low values. For example, using Design 1 on Radar X with a high Power value of 405.6 watts and a low Power value of 218.4 watts, the transformation equation is:

$$\frac{X - 312}{93.6} \quad (1)$$

Once the range for each radar was calculated, a stepwise regression program was used to apply the technique of response surface methodology to the calculated data.

Assumption

It is assumed that the values chosen for the parameters not in the database (radar cross section, temperature, probability of false alarm, probability of detection, and number of pulses incoherently integrated) are appropriate.

III. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Fractional Factorial Designs

When the initial runs were analyzed, the adjusted R-squared values averaged approximately 0.97. The residual plots, however, indicated a quadratic tendency.

Due to this strong dependence shown in the residual plots, a transformation of the data was needed. (1:210) This transformation was accomplished by computing the logarithm of the range as the output of the Fortran program. Once this transformation was complete, the designs were run again. The residual plot revealed no dependent relationship, and thus a more accurate estimation of the data resulted. The R-squared value and adjusted R-squared value for all four designs were both 1.0. The following is a summary of the significant effects from radar X from each design:

Table VIII. Significant Effects* Using the Fractional Factorial Design for Designs 1-4

Design	1	2	3	4
PD	PD	PD	GT	GT
P	GT	GR	GR	GR
PFA	GR	PD	PD	PD
GT	P	P	P	P
GR	PFA	PFA	PFA	PFA
RCS	RCS	RCS	F	F
N	N	N	RCS	RCS
F	F	F	N	N
PFAPD	NF	NF	NF	NF
NF	PFAPD	B	B	B
PFAN	L	L	L	L
L	B	PFAPD	PFAPD	PFAPD
B	PFAN	PFAN	PFAN	PFAN
T	T	T	T	T
PDN	PDN	PDN	PDN	PDN

*The letters PFAPD, PFAN, and PDN denote the two-way interactions of the probability of false alarm and probability of detection, probability of false alarm and number of pulses incoherently integrated, and probability of detection and number of pulses integrated respectively.

Linear Equations

The linear equation using the fractional factorial design for radar X using each design (1-4) is as follows:

Table IX. Linear Equations using the Fractional Factorial Design for Designs 1-4

Design 1			
5.493	- 0.254PD	+ 0.204P	+ 0.137PFA
+ 0.123GT	+ 0.113GR	+ 0.097RCS	+ 0.089N
- 0.030F	- 0.024PFAPD	- 0.023NF	- 0.012PFAN
- 0.011L	- 0.011B	- 0.005T	+ 0.004PDN
Design 2			
5.496	- 0.254PD	+ 0.247GT	+ 0.227GR
+ 0.215P	+ 0.137PFA	+ 0.097RCS	+ 0.089N
- 0.053F	- 0.045NF	- 0.024PFAPD	- 0.023L
- 0.022B	- 0.012PFAN	- 0.005T	+ 0.004PDN
Design 3			
5.502	+ 0.370GT	+ 0.340GR	- 0.254PD
+ 0.227P	+ 0.137PFA	+ 0.097RCS	+ 0.089N
- 0.076F	- 0.060NF	- 0.034B	- 0.030L
- 0.024PFAPD	- 0.012PFAN	- 0.005T	+ 0.004PDN
Design 4			
5.510	+ 0.493GT	+ 0.453GR	- 0.254PD
+ 0.239P	+ 0.137PFA	- 0.101F	+ 0.097RCS
+ 0.089N	- 0.075NF	- 0.046B	- 0.0375L
- 0.024PFAPD	- 0.012PFAN	- 0.005T	+ 0.004PDN

Full Factorial Designs

Since the fractional factorial designs were analyzed and it was discovered that they contained some error, albeit less than 10%, a full factorial design was run for the radar. Since this radar contains 12 factors, this required 4096 runs. The results are as follows:

Table X. R-Squared and Adjusted R-Squared Values for Design 3 using the Full Factorial Design

R-Squared	.9982
Adjusted R-Squared	.9982

Table XI. Significant Effects using the Full Factorial Design for Design 3

GT
GR
PD
P
PFA
RCS
N
F
NF
B
L
T

The fractional factorial design contained some "noise" and introduced the two-way interaction terms to account for this. As can be seen from this table, the full factorial design contains no two-way interaction terms and thus less "noise". Two-way interactions were not expected in these designs (except PFA, PD, and N because the interactions of these factors was not known) because the radar range equation is linear in the logarithmic scale, thus no interaction among the terms.

Table XII. Linear Equation using the Full Factorial Design for Design 3

5.502	+ 0.370GT	+ 0.340GR	- 0.254PD
+ 0.227P	+ 0.137PFA	+ 0.097RCS	+ 0.089N
- 0.076F	- 0.060NF	- 0.034B	- 0.030L
- 0.005T			

As can be seen from above, the full factorial design mainly reinforces the design created for the 12 factor case. The significant effects were in the exact same order, and the coefficients were identical.

Reduced Models

Using the standard of an R-squared of 99% the significant effects from design 3 for radar X were chosen. The following shows the significant effects for the radar to achieve a 99% R-squared using design 3.

Table XIII. Significant Effects for the Reduced Models using an R-Squared Value of 99%

GT
GR
PD
P
PFA
RCS
N
F
NF

To achieve a 99% model R-squared, some radars might need more effects than others. This indicates the degree of accuracy needed for a particular radar. If there were many significant effects, the radar could only be modeled effectively using them all and has been estimated accurately. If there were few effects, this indicates that only a few variables are significant and thus much more accuracy is needed to reduce their significance so other factors become significant. For example, suppose a radar uses 10 of its 12 variables to estimate its range whereas another radar uses only 6 out of 11. This indicates that in the first radar the estimation of the parameters was sufficiently accurate relative to their relationship in the radar range equation.

Linear Equations

The linear equation for each radar using a reduced design of the significant effects above while maintaining an R-squared value of 99%, is as follows:

Table XIV. Linear Equation using the Reduced Model for Design 3

5.502	+	0.370GT	+	0.340GR	-	0.254PD
+0.227P	+	0.137PFA	+	0.097RCS	+	0.089N
-0.076F	-	0.060NF				

Maximum Ranges

The following is the maximum range in miles for radar X. The arrow at the bottom left of the figure refers to the maximum range of the radar at its optimum setting without regard to the confidence factors. The legend denotes the maximum range calculated using the reduced design (REDUCED in legend) (far left bar of each set), the full factorial design (FULL in legend) (left center of each set), the Fortran program (FORTRAN in legend) (right center of each set), and the fractional factorial design (FRACTION in legend) (far right of each set).

Figure 2. Radar X Maximum Ranges

As can be seen from above, the most accurate estimation of the maximum range is the full factorial design, then the fractional factorial design, and lastly the reduced design. The difference between the range calculated using the Fortran program and the range calculated using the full linear equation is due to the error inherent in the "linearizing" of the radar range equation. However, the error was never greater than 3%.

Since the fractional factorial design is only a partial of the full design, not all possible combinations are included. The optimum combination of:

Table XV. Optimal Settings for Maximum Radar Range

P	GT	GR	F	NF	L	B	RCS	T	PFA	PD	N
1	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	1

is not included in the fractional factorial design. The maximum range within this design is not necessarily the maximum range of the radar. Thus the ranges given are the best from the fractional factorial design and will have some error.

The reason the fractional factorial designs have maximum ranges greater than the calculated ranges is due to error. The fractional factorial design tries to estimate the data with 12 factors. In trying to estimate this data with a linear equation, some points (the maximum range point) will not be on this line, and thus this distance is the error.

The main ideas that must be remembered, the full linear design is used to identify the significant effects thus allowing to create a reduced design. The reduced design is created to allow the database user to change a variable while noting the change in the range of the radar. The full linear equation can be used for this purpose but it is a little more difficult due to the number of settings and it contains some error.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Implications

As can be seen from the table of significant effects, as the degree of inaccuracy of estimation increases (confidence factor increases) the importance of the variables in the radar equation increases. All variables, gain, frequency, noise figure, bandwidth, losses, and power increase in importance if they are not estimated accurately. The variables, probability of detection, probability of false alarm, radar cross section, and number of pulses integrated decrease in importance as the confidence factor increases (estimations become more inaccurate). This indicates the relative importance of the variables due to the inherent relationship in the radar range equation and the degree of accuracy required in estimating them. The importance of this finding is that this indicates which variables to concentrate the most time and money on data collection, since these variables significantly affect the range of the radar set. The most important factor to be estimated with the highest degree of accuracy is antenna gain. This factor in all radars quickly becomes significant when not estimated accurately.

The range of the radar set also varies if the confidence factor in the database is used. As can be seen from the difference in range from design 0 to even design 1 this can be very significant. The confidence factors must be incorporated when calculating range to include this degree of inaccuracy.

Recommendations

The calculation of radar ranges within the database must use the confidence factors associated with the parameters. This gives a database user a more "accurate" capability of a radar's range.

The estimation of the radar antenna gain should be the single most important goal in data collection. The other factors of a radar's range were significant, but none were as significant as the antenna gain.

Future Research

Goal programming can be employed using the linear equations to maximize the range if constraints of the factors involved are known. Given a desired maximum range, the linear equations could be used to meet this goal subject to cost constraints on the individual constituents.

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